

Lateral cracking at linear sharp contacts

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A fracture mechanics analysis is developed for lateral cracking at linear sharp contacts. Such contacts are commonly encountered as surface scratches formed by loaded wedges, rolled particles, or dragged asperities. The most visible features of a scratch are the lateral cracks extending parallel to the surface from the linear contact. The analysis here takes an energy-based approach to predict lateral crack length as functions of contact load and geometry and material modulus, hardness, and toughness, independent of the scratch origin. The basis of the analysis is the relaxation of residual elastic energy associated with contact deformation and conversion into surface energy associated with lateral cracking. The analysis is supported by experimental measurements of cracks from dragged and rolled contacts. The analysis is applied in derivation of the mineralogical Mohs scale, providing a fundamental basis for the scale in terms of material properties and a clear definition of scratch resistance supported by experiment. The need for more measurements in this field is highlighted.

Cite as:

Cook, Robert F. (2020, October 22). Lateral cracking at linear sharp contacts (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4119092>

1. INTRODUCTION

Sharp contacts on brittle material surfaces generate two major fracture systems: the “median-radial” system, in which cracks extend perpendicular to the surface from the contact [Lawn *et al.*, 1980]; and the “lateral” system, in which cracks extend parallel to the surface from the contact [Marshall *et al.*, 1982]. The first of these has received the most attention as it is predominant in determining failure behavior of brittle components. Sharp contact flaws in brittle materials such as ceramics, glasses, semiconductors, rocks, and minerals are characterized by localized plastic deformation zones and extended elastic deformation fields remaining after the contact event. These “residual” fields both initiate median-radial cracks and significantly enhance crack propagation under the action of superposed applied stress. As a consequence, if a contact on a component is large enough, the ensuing flaw, consisting of medial-radial cracks + residual field, is strength-controlling. Deliberately introduced sharp indentation flaws, such as formed by Vickers pyramidal diamond probes, thus act as model flaws for studying the fracture behavior of structural ceramics and other brittle materials, including estimating toughness through measurement of surface traces of median-radial cracks [Anstis *et al.*, 1981; Cook, 2020] and determining the effects of microstructure and environment on toughness through indentation-strength measurements [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981; Cook, 2015].

Observations of sharp contact flaws, however, particularly indentation flaws generated in the conventional load ranges of most indenters, 10–100 N, quickly reveal that it is the second crack system above, lateral cracks extending almost parallel to the contacted surface, that is the most visible. The air gap and concomitant surface uplift associated with lateral cracks generate significant contrast on optical observation of sharp contact flaws, particularly in bright- and dark-field optical microscopy [Marshall *et al.*, 1982], rendering lateral cracks the largest and most obvious feature. This is particularly so at large contact loads when lateral cracks curve and extend to the material surface, removing conchoidal chips of material from the surface adjacent to the contact [Cook *et al.*, 1990]. Such lateral cracking or chipping degrades the optical properties of surfaces, is responsible for material removal under erosive conditions, and

significantly affects median-radial based strength and toughness analyses through modification of the residual stress field [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015].

Here, lateral cracks at sharp *linear* contacts are considered. Such cracks are often the most visible evidence of accidental contacts leading to “scratches” by static, rolled, or dragged sharp objects or particles. The analogous deliberate contacts leading to linear flaws are those generated by (i) static sharp edges or corners on load bearing surfaces, (ii) rolling bevelled disk cutters used to score glass or tile for breaking, (iii) dragged sharp scribes used to scratch markings or score lines into surfaces. (Contacts restricted to a single location, such as indentations, are considered *point* flaws.)

Figure 1. Reflected light plan view image of a surface flaw in glass generated by linear sharp contact with a rolled disk cutter. The central contact track and extensive lateral cracks are visible.

An example of a sharp linear contact flaw on a brittle surface is given in Fig. 1, which shows an optical brightfield plan view of a flaw generated by a disk cutter rolled manually on soda-lime silicate glass. The residual surface track, indicating plastic deformation of the glass at the cutter contact, is visible as the straight line at the center of the flaw, width $2w$; track contrast is

associated with residual surface deformation. The sub-surface lateral cracks, indicating fracture of the glass, are visible as bright undulating areas either side of the track, width $2c$; contrast is associated with the air gap and reflection from the lower cracked surface. The lateral cracks are clearly much larger than the track. The sub-surface median crack is not visible. Similar images have been reported in recent works using commercial scratch testers to generate surface damage in glass by dragged sharp probes [Gu and Yao, 2011; Bensaid *et al.*, 2018; Suratwala *et al.*, 2019; Zakiev *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2020].

Figure 2. Cross-section images of a linear sharp contact flaw in glass formed by a disk roller. (a) Reflected light image. (b) Transmitted cross-polarized light image.

Greater detail of a sharp linear contact flaw generated by a rolling disk cutter is shown in Fig. 2. Figure 2(a) shows a flaw in soda-lime glass similar to Fig. 1 but in a reflected light brightfield cross section. The location on the glass surface of the contact track and associated plastic deformation zone is visible at the top of the image. A median crack extends perpendicular to the surface from the base of zone. Lateral cracks extend approximately parallel to the surface from near the base of the zone. Figure 2(b) is a transmitted cross-polarized light image of the same flaw. The large areas of reversed contrast are indicative of birefringence induced by the extended residual stress and strain fields about the flaw. Cross-section images very similar to Fig. 2(a), showing a contact track, plastic deformation zone, median crack, and lateral cracks have been reported since the early studies of linear flaws, including: scratches formed by dragged Vickers probes on glass [Peter, 1964; Evers, 1967; Swain, 1979]; scratches formed by single point grinding of Al_2O_3 [Gruver and Kirchner, 1973], glass [Swain, 1979; Kirchner, 1984], and Si_3N_4 [Kirchner and Isaacson, 1982]; scratches formed by multipoint grinding of glass [Kirchner, 1984] and Si [Pei *et al.*, 1999]; line flaws formed by static sharp wedge loading of glass and rock [Swain and Lawn, 1976]; and line flaws formed by rolled disk cutters on glass [Howes and Szameitat, 1984]. Cross-sections of line flaws formed by sharp wedge micro indentation of film-on-substrate systems are also similar to Fig. 2(a), showing contact tracks and plastic deformation zones in the film, median cracks in the substrate, and lateral delamination cracks at the film-substrate interface [Yeap *et al.*, 2007] along with associated film uplift [De Boer and Gerberich, 1996]. Polarized light cross sections similar to Fig. 2(b), showing significant birefringence indicative of residual stress fields, have been reported for linear flaws in glass formed by rolled disk cutters [Swain, 1981a; Symonds *et al.*, 1983]. Longitudinal sections of multiple indentation arrays and grinding tracks on Si_3N_4 show great similarity and exhibit behavior consistent with a significant residual field [Marshall *et al.*, 1983]. The implication from the above works is that the phenomenology of deformation and cracking at linear sharp contacts is well established, typified by Figs. 1 and 2, and extends across material classes and contact types, thereby providing a firm foundation for analysis.

Early fracture mechanics analyses of linear flaws generated by sharp contacts were performed in the 1980s, primarily by Swain in the context of rolled contacts during glass cutting

and Kirchner in the context of dragged contacts during ceramic grinding and machining. The focus of these researchers was the formation of median cracks during contact and subsequent crack propagation to failure under the action of applied stress. Prediction of component strength was a predominant goal. The contributions of Kirchner and Swain are summarized and reviewed by the current author in two subsequent works considering deformation and fracture at linear flaws generated by rolled [Cook, 1994] and dragged [Cook, 2017] contacts on glass and Al_2O_3 , respectively. Although these latter works advanced the fracture mechanics significantly, the emphasis was still on median cracks and strength. However, a broadly-applicable central feature of these works was separation of the factors leading to track and plastic deformation zone formation—the load and geometry of rolled, dragged, or wedge contacts—from the influence of the track and zone in fracture mechanics analyses. As a consequence, the fracture mechanics framework developed in these later works self-consistently describes and predicts track dimensions, median crack lengths, and component strengths, including measurements from the earlier and other [Cook, 2018] works, along with the effects of material microstructure and lateral crack related stress relaxation at large contact loads.

The matrix of phenomena, sharp point contact, sharp linear contact, median crack length, and lateral crack length is then complete except for the last element—the lengths of lateral cracks at sharp linear contacts. The work here develops the fracture mechanics to address this omission. As in the earlier works [Cook, 1994, 2017], a key element of the analysis will be separation of contact and fracture details. A primary focus is to enable estimates of surface and edge quality and material removal by linear contacts and scratches. A secondary focus is more philosophical and is concerned with understanding the scratch hardness test and related Mohs scale. The work begins with an analysis section that first considers linear contacts and then considers linear lateral cracks. The results section then follows and compares behavior observed for dragged and rolled contacts with predictions from the analysis. A discussion places the work here in the context of previous lateral crack analyses, considers engineering applications, and suggests some interpretations of the Mohs scale.

2. ANALYSIS

Lateral cracks at linear sharp contacts are described here by fracture mechanics analysis based on energy changes associated with cracking after contact. The analysis leads to results analogous to those obtained earlier based on force balances at point contacts on monolithic materials [Marshall *et al.*, 1982] and at film on substrate systems [Marshall and Evans, 1984; Rossington *et al.*, 1984; Ritter *et al.*, 1989; Rosenfeld *et al.*, 1990; Thurn and Cook, 2004]. The energy approach provides insight into the origin of the force balances by recognizing three interrelated internal energy changes on cracking after contact, two associated with elastic deformation and one associated with surface formation. Analysis begins by consideration of the contact deformation process followed by consideration of the energy changes associated with subsequent lateral cracking.

2.1. Contact deformation

Figure 3 shows a cross-section of a deformation and fracture sequence at a linear sharp contact. In Fig. 3(a), the section is at peak load, characterized by a contact or track width of $2w$ and a sharp contact or probe included angle of $2\phi_p$. The contact extends perpendicular to the image, consisting of many sections along the contact length. For static contact by a linear sharp wedge of length L , all cross-sections along L are identical. For a peak load P imposed on such a wedge, the peak line load, load/length, imposed on the material is $P_L = P/L$ and is identical at all sections, as are w and ϕ_p . (Throughout, all line quantities are indicated by subscript L, “ X_L ”.) Contact between the probe and the surface is characterized by the mean supported contact stress, the hardness H , given by

$$H = P_L/2w. \quad (1)$$

An example is a $2w \times L = 0.1 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ contact on a $H = 10 \text{ GPa}$ material, for which $P = 10 \text{ kN}$; wedge loads are large [Swain and Lawn, 1976]. For a rigid probe, the contact depth d_p at peak load is given by

$$d_p = w \cot \phi_p. \quad (2)$$

Deformation of the material by the probe is both elastic and plastic. For brittle materials, plastic deformation is localized to a small zone bounded at the surface by the contact (in this case the track width) and in the subsurface by a characteristic depth, h_p . Elastic deformation is extended, including surface deformation exterior to the contact and bulk deformation interior and exterior to the plastic deformation zone boundary. At peak load, the transverse stress on the median plane bisecting the contact, is tensile, leading to the formation of a median vent or median crack on this plane directly beneath the contact. These cracks can control the strength of components containing linear contact flaws and are used by glaziers to break glass and ceramics from scored surfaces. Median cracks are considered elsewhere [Cook, 1994, 2017, 2018].

For rolling or dragged contacts, all sections along the contact are not identical. In these more common cases, the contact width, included angle, and line load vary along the length of the contact according to the transverse contact profile (*e.g.*, circular for a glass cutting disk rollers, triangular for dragged indenters). For such contacts, the cross section of Fig. 3(a), and w , ϕ_p , and P_L , pertain to the location of maximum contact depth associated with the moving profile. Variations in these quantities along the length of the contact lead to non-linear relationships between the value of P_L effective during fracture at a linear flaw and the physical load P applied in flaw formation. The simplest of these relationships is that for a dragged fixed profile probe such as an indenter, for which $P_L \sim P^{1/2}$ [Cook, 2017]. (Throughout, the symbol \sim indicates “varies as.”) For simplicity, the wedge picture is borne in mind throughout the following, but the lateral crack analysis developed is general and describes linear flaws formed by static, rolling, or dragging contacts. The focus of analysis is on the residual geometry after contact, rather than the loads active during contact. Connection with observation or experiment and with the physical load P is made after the analysis, and is considered here in the Results section.

(a) Peak Load

(b) Unload

(c) Fracture

Figure 3. Schematic cross sections of a sharp contact deformation and fracture sequence in the formation of a linear flaw. (a) Peak load, consisting of elastic-plastic deformation. (b) Unload, consisting of elastic recovery. (c) Fracture, consisting of stress relaxation by lateral crack formation.

On unloading, Fig. 3(b), elastic contact deformation is recovered, leaving a residual contact impression, the track, associated with plastic deformation. Here, obtuse probes ($2\phi_p > 120^\circ$) are considered, for which there is very little elastic deformation transverse to the contact. The recovered surface is characterized by a track of residual depth $d < d_p$ given by

$$d = w \cot \phi, \quad (3)$$

where $2\phi > 2\phi_p$ is the residual included angle and the track width w is taken as invariant from peak load to the unloaded state. An example is $\phi \simeq 76^\circ$ such that $\cot \phi \simeq 1/4$, typical for a scratch generated by a dragged Vickers indenter. The scale of the residual plastic deformation zone can be estimated by modeling the contact as a pressurized cylindrical cavity in an elastic-perfectly plastic medium [Hill, 1950], assuming that the scaling extends to the half-space of the contacted material. At peak load the (half-space) cross-sectional area of the cavity is taken to be the contact cross-section, $w d_p$, and the pressure exerted on the surrounding material is H . H is also taken as the measure of material resistance to plastic yielding (consistent with the lack of transverse recovery of the track width) such that an (approximately hemicylindrical) plastic deformation zone forms about the contact. Recovery on unloading decreases the cross-sectional areas of both the track, to its residual value of $w d$, and the plastic deformation zone, to a characteristic value $h^2 < h_p^2$, such that mechanical equilibrium is established over the cross-section between the hydrostatically compressed plastic deformation zone and the surrounding elastically restraining matrix. The pressurized cylindrical cavity analysis implies variation of h with material properties and track geometry as [Cook, 1985],

$$h \sim w (E/H)^{2/3} (\cot \phi)^{1/2}, \quad (4)$$

where E here is the material plane strain Young's modulus. Relation (4) is similar in form to that developed earlier for an analogous spherical cavity model applied to point contacts [Lawn *et al.*, 1980], and, in comparison to Eq. (3), introduces materials dependence and diminished contact geometry dependence, consistent with the elastic-plastic deformation configuration.

Independent of the formation mechanism and any material influences, for a flaw of length L the dilatational strain, Δ_r , developed in the residual plastic deformation zone is given by

$$\Delta_r \sim - w d L / h^2 L \sim - w^2 \cot \phi / h^2. \quad (5)$$

The (volumetric) elastic energy density, \mathcal{U}_E , in a cross section of the flaw varies as

$$\mathcal{U}_E \sim \Delta_r^2 \quad (6)$$

such that the total residual elastic energy in the system, U_r , is given by

$$U_r = (M/2)(w^4 \cot^2 \phi / h^4) h^2 L,$$

and the elastic line energy, U_{rL} , of the flaw is thus

$$U_{rL} = (M/2)(w^4 \cot^2 \phi / h^4) h^2. \quad (7)$$

The parameter M is an elastic modulus that takes into account the exact geometries of the plastic deformation zone and the stress and strain fields in a cross section of the flaw (zone + matrix). Equation (7) represents elastic potential energy stored in the material as a result of work performed by the contact during flaw formation. The energy is analogous to that stored in a one-dimensional deformed linear spring. Rewriting Eq. (7) as

$$U_{rL} = (M/E^2)(E w^2 \cot \phi / h)^2 / 2$$

suggests the definition of two quantities associated with the residual plastic deformation zone,

$$\lambda_{rL} = M/E^2 \quad (8a)$$

and

$$F_{rL} = E w^2 \cot \phi / h \quad (8b)$$

as a line compliance and line force, respectively. The introduction of the plane strain Young's modulus E is recognition of the one-dimensional nature of the spring. The elastic line energy of Eq. (7) is then expressed as

$$U_{rL} = \lambda_{rL} F_{rL}^2 / 2 \quad (9)$$

or, alternatively, defining a displacement conjugate to the force by

$$u_r = -\lambda_{rL} F_{rL}, \quad (10)$$

the elastic line energy is expressed as

$$U_{rL} = u_r^2 / 2 \lambda_{rL}. \quad (11)$$

It is noted that

$$u_r = -M w^2 \cot \phi / E h < 0$$

and thus it is convenient to define the magnitude $\delta = |u_r|$. In arithmetic terms, Eqs, (9)–(11) have the familiar forms describing a spring, in which u_r is the displacement of the spring

from its natural length and F_{rL} is the force exerted by the displaced spring on its surroundings. Here, u_r is negative—the spring is deformed to a shorter length—and F_{rL} is positive—relative to the spring, the force is outward. In physical terms, the spring is the plastic deformation zone exerting a force to push the zone out of the constraining matrix. Relaxing the constraint reduces the elastic line energy deriving from the contact imposed dilatational strain, Eq. (5). Lateral crack formation associated with such relaxation is considered in the next section.

2.2. Lateral cracking

Figure 3(c) shows the configuration of a linear sharp contact with lateral cracks. A coordinate axis that is positive along the material outward normal and fixed in the material is implicit. Three changes are apparent relative to the uncracked configuration of Fig. 3(b). First, crack opening displacement at the crack mouths extends the plastic deformation zone, leading to surface uplift relative to the coordinate fixed point at the intersection of the zone and the matrix. Second, the displacement and surface uplift cause bending deformation of material in the matrix adjacent to the plastic deformation zone. Third, crack extension leads to the creation of new surfaces in the matrix. The effects of these changes on system energy are considered in turn.

Crack opening displacement leads to expansion of the plastic deformation zone and thus relaxation of the compressed spring and reduction in the residual elastic line energy. Rewriting Eq. (8b) to include a small extension of the zone $h \rightarrow h(1 + z/\delta)$ by crack opening displacement $z \geq 0$, Fig. 3(c), leads to modification of Eq. (9), $U_{rL} \rightarrow U_{rL}/(1 + z/\delta)^2 \simeq U_{rL}(1 - z/\delta)^2$. Equation (11) is thus generalized to

$$U_{EL} = (\delta - z)^2/2\lambda_{rL}. \quad (12)$$

Crack opening displacement also leads to deformation in the matrix that is well approximated by the bending of two cantilevers. The cantilevers are formed by the material and lateral crack surfaces with fixed ends built in to the matrix and free ends displaced by the extending plastic deformation zone. The line energy of the deformed cantilevers is given by

$$U_{CL} = z^2/2\lambda_{cL}, \quad (13)$$

where λ_{cL} is the line compliance of the two cantilever system,

$$\lambda_{cL} = 2c^3/Eh^3, \quad (14)$$

and c is the lateral crack length that defines the length of an individual cantilever.

The formation of the lateral cracks generates new fractures surface in the material with surface energy areal density 2γ . As there are two cracks the crack area/length is $2c$, such that the surface energy/length of the lateral cracks is

$$U_{SL} = 4c\gamma. \quad (15)$$

The total line energy of the lateral crack fracture system is the sum of Eqs. (12), (13), and (15),

$$\begin{aligned} U_L &= U_{EL} + U_{CL} + U_{SL} \\ &= (\delta - z)^2/2\lambda_{rL} + z^2/2\lambda_{cL} + 4c\gamma \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

It is noted that the energy of Eq. (16) depends on two extensive system variables, z and c , and hence there are two forces associated with two different derivatives of the energy. The first of these is

$$\begin{aligned} F_L(z) &= -\partial U_L/\partial z = F_{EL} + F_{CL} \\ &= (\delta - z)/\lambda_{rL} - z/\lambda_{cL}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

which expresses the net crack opening force as the competing sum of the spring force associated with the residual plastic deformation zone attempting to open the crack and the cantilevers attempting to close the crack, noting that the third, surface energy, term plays no role. Mechanical equilibrium is determined by setting $F_L = 0$ in Eq. (17) to give

$$z = \delta/(1 + Mh^3/2Ec^3), \quad (18)$$

using Eqs. (8a) and (14) and noting that as a function of c Eq. (18) describes a range of equilibrium configurations. Consideration of Eq. (17) shows that $\partial F_L/\partial z < 0$ such that the equilibria are stable.

The second force associated with a derivative of the total energy is, using Eq. (14),

$$\begin{aligned} F_L(c) &= -\partial U_L/\partial(2c) = \mathcal{G} - R \\ &= 3Eh^3z^2/2c^4 - 2\gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

which expresses the net crack extension force as the difference between the mechanical energy release rate \mathcal{G} associated with the cantilevers attempting to extend the crack and the fracture resistance R associated with the surface energy attempting to retract the crack. \mathcal{G} and R are

configurational forces associated with crack area changes in the system and are the conventional terms used in fracture mechanics [Lawn, 1993]. Note the absence of the minus sign in the definition of R . Fracture equilibrium is determined by setting $\mathcal{G} = R$ in Eq. (19), noting that such a condition here describes a range of equilibrium configurations as it is a function of z .

Specification of an equilibrium crack configuration begins by combining z from Eq. (18) into the definition of \mathcal{G} from Eq. (19) to give, after some manipulation,

$$\mathcal{G} = 6(U_{rL}/h) \left[\frac{\xi(c/h)}{1 + \xi^2(c/h)^3} \right]^2, \quad (20)$$

where $\xi^2 = (2E/M)$ is a dimensionless geometry factor of order unity. Equation (20) shows that \mathcal{G} is the product of an energy/area, (U_{rL}/h) , and a dimensionless function of relative crack length, (c/h) . Equation (20) has several interpretations and applications. The first interpretation is that Eq. (20) embodies the physics of first law of thermodynamics by describing energy associated with surface creation in terms of energy associated with elastic deformation (which was in turn generated by work performed by the contact). The second interpretation is to recognize that $\mathcal{G}(c)$ in Eq. (20) passes through a maximum at $(c/h) = (2\xi^2)^{1/3}$ and thus Eq. (20) represents a destabilizing to stabilizing transition at the maximum and thus embodies the fracture mechanics of crack initiation. Such fracture mechanics has been well studied for median-radial cracks at indentation contacts in ceramics [Lawn and Evans, 1977; Lawn and Marshall, 1979], cracks at phase-transforming expanding inclusions in glass [Swain, 1981b], and cracks at constrained conducting lines in microelectronic dielectrics [Thurn and Cook, 2002]. The first application of Eq. (20) is then to build on these analyses and recognize that the imposition of the equilibrium condition $\mathcal{G} = 2\gamma$ at the maximum of $\mathcal{G}(c)$ leads to a minimum value of U_{rL} required to generate lateral cracks at a linear sharp contact. Such “threshold” effects are commonly observed and are of great engineering importance in designing scratch and mar free surfaces.

The second, and perhaps more important, application of Eq. (20) is to consider the behavior of $\mathcal{G}(c)$ on the stabilizing branch well away from the maximum at $(c/h) \gg 1$, such that

$$\mathcal{G} = 6(U_{rL}/h)/\xi^2(c/h)^4. \quad (21)$$

For fixed profile contacts (ϕ is invariant with contact depth), such as by static wedges, dragged indenters, or conical rollers, deformation on a track cross section maintains geometrical similarity, such that $h \sim w$ and thus $U_{rL} \sim Mw^2$ (Eq. 7) and Eq. (21) is simply expressed as

$$\mathcal{E} \sim Mw^5/c^4, \quad (22)$$

which is indeed stabilizing as $\partial\mathcal{E}/\partial c < 0$. The importance of Eq. (22) is that imposing the equilibrium condition gives the variation of lateral crack length in terms of track width in experimentally testable terms, $c \sim w^{5/4}$. Further, the mechanism by which the track was generated was not specified, such that Eq. (22) can be expressed in terms of the most commonly controlled contact parameter, the normal load P . As discussed above, for static wedges, $w \sim P$, Eq. (1), such that $c \sim P^{5/4}$. For dragged indenters, $w \sim P^{1/2}$, such that $c \sim P^{5/8}$. For conical rollers, $w \sim P^{2/3}$, such that $c \sim P^{5/6}$. These latter two relations, pertaining to the most common experimental conditions, will be examined in the next section.

3. RESULTS

Linear sharp contact data are considered here, making use of the above analysis regarding lateral crack lengths in interpreting three sets of results of increasing complexity. The first set considers a single fixed-profile pyramidal indenter dragged on three materials to generate lateral cracks at different contact loads. The second set considers multiple conical glass cutters rolled on a single material to generate lateral cracks with different contact geometries at different contact loads. The third set considers sharp contacts dragged so as to form scratches on the ten different minerals that constitute the archetypes in the Mohs scale. The lateral crack analysis is applied to evaluate resistance to scratching in terms of plastic, fracture, and wear properties of the Mohs minerals.

3.1. Dragged contacts

Figure 4 shows a logarithmic plot of track width w and lateral crack length c as a function of normal contact load P for two glasses and single crystal sapphire (Al_2O_3). The contact tracks and

cracks were generated by dragging a Vickers diamond at 0.125 mm s^{-1} on the material surfaces. The data are taken from the published results of Swain [Swain, 1979]. The lower, filled, symbols indicate the track widths and the lower line is a guide to the eye of slope $1/2$, consistent with the $w \sim (P/H)^{1/2}$ response expected for scratched tracks on materials of constant hardness H [Cook, 2017]. The track widths are consistent with constant hardness and the hardest material sapphire exhibits the smallest tracks and the glasses larger tracks. The upper, open, symbols indicate the lateral crack lengths. Simple imposition of the equilibrium condition $\mathcal{E} = 2\gamma$ in Eq. (22) and inverting gives $c^4 \sim w^5/(2\gamma M)$. Replacing w with the contact load using the above relation and suppressing material and geometrical effects gives,

$$c \sim P^{5/8}. \quad (23)$$

The upper line in Fig. 4 is a guide to the eye of slope $5/8$, consistent with the $w \sim P^{5/8}$ response from Eq. (23). Despite some scatter, the data are consistent with this expected trend. The lateral crack length is anticipated to be smaller in harder and tougher materials, and this is the case, sapphire exhibited the smallest cracks. Overall, the quantitative trends in Fig. 4 are consistent with the analysis developed here and a step beyond the empirical power laws used earlier.

Figure 4. Plot of scratch dimensions as a function of normal contact load for linear flaws formed by a dragged Vickers indenter. Raw data taken from from Swain [Swain, 1979]. Lines indicate behavior consistent with constant hardness and toughness.

3.2. Rolled contacts

Lateral crack lengths at roller tracks are compared here for rollers of different conical geometry, radius R and included angle ϕ , contacting a single soda-lime glass material. Hence, Eq. (21) is re-expressed as

$$G \sim w^5 \cot \phi / c^4 \quad (24)$$

by including a geometrical rather than a material dependence from Eq. (7). Track width for roller flaws including a geometrical dependence is [Cook, 1994]

$$w \sim P^{2/3} (R \cot \phi)^{-1/3}. \quad (25)$$

Imposing equilibrium, combining Eqs. (24) and (25), and inverting leads to

$$c \sim [P / (R \cot^{2/5} \phi)^{1/2}]^{5/6}, \quad (26)$$

which shows the predominant $P^{5/6}$ dependence for lateral cracks generated at roller tracks, with lesser influences of roller radius and included angle.

Figure 5. Plot of lateral crack lengths at linear flaws generated by disk roller contacts using ranges of normal contact loads and roller radii and included angles. Raw data provided by Swain [Swain, 1985]. Abscissa coordinate adjusts contact load to compare different roller shapes.

Following Eq. (26), Fig. 5 shows a logarithmic plot of lateral crack length c as a function of the adjusted normal contact load parameter $P/(R\cot^{2/5}\phi)^{1/2}$ for conical roller flaws formed on soda lime glass. The flaws were generated by nine different hard metal rollers with radii between 2.75 mm and 1.85 mm and included semi-angles between 75° and 42.5° rolled at approximately 0.5 mm s^{-1} on the glass surface. The raw data are from the unpublished results of Swain [Swain, 1985]. The line in Fig. 5 is a guide to the eye of slope $5/6$, consistent with the response from Eq. (26). Despite some scatter, the data are consistent with this expected trend.

3.3. Mohs scale minerals

The Mohs scale was originally developed as a method to guide mineral identification. The method qualitatively ranks ten standard minerals by increasing resistance to scratching by a file or standard mineral. Scratch resistance is assessed by width and depth of the residual scratch leading to a ranking on the scale from 1, least scratch resistant, archetype talc, to 10, most scratch resistant, archetype diamond. The intermediate archetype minerals include calcite, 3, and quartz, 7. The scale is often referred to as a “hardness” scale, although it has long been known that the assessments of Mohs number for many materials do not vary linearly or even monotonically with conventional hardness measurements. The lack of clear understanding of the Mohs scale stems in large part from the lack of clear definition of what constitutes “scratch resistance,” what the width and depth of a residual scratch represent—plasticity, fracture, or wear—or how this combination of phenomena varies from material to material. This issue was addressed in an earlier comprehensive work that used indentation techniques to measure the modulus, hardness, and toughness of the Mohs scale minerals at scratch-relevant length scales [Broz *et al.*, 2006]. This work also included a brief history of the Mohs scale and its historical relationship to hardness, and although recognizing the importance of material hardness in the development of the Mohs scale, concluded that “other properties such as toughness and modulus are involved in the phenomenon of scratch resistance” and “Until the physical processes of cracking associated with scratching vs. indentation are studied in more detail, the best explanation is that scratch resistance is fundamentally different from hardness, and that fracture

toughness may dominate in some minerals. There is no simple way to predict the relationship of material properties and Mohs number.” This section uses the lateral crack analysis developed above to address the problems raised in these conclusions.

The approach here is to examine three candidate phenomena that give rise to a visually apparent scratch when a sharp contact is dragged on a surface. These phenomena are plastic deformation, quantified by the track width w , fracture, quantified by the lateral crack length c , and the line wear volume, V_L , a new parameter quantifying the volume of material removed per length of scratch. The variations of the spatial parameters, w , c , and V_L , are predicted from the material properties of modulus, hardness, and toughness, E , H , and T using the values for Mohs minerals developed by Broz [Broz *et al.*, 2006]. Scratch resistance is predicted by the inverse comparison of parameters, for example, shorter lateral crack lengths imply a greater relative scratch resistance. Predicted scratch resistance is then compared with the Mohs number.

The simplest spatial parameter to quantify is the track width w , which for dragged contacts of fixed included angle varies with contact load and material hardness as

$$w \sim (P/H)^{1/2}. \quad (27)$$

Contacts at which scratch damage is determined by plastic deformation alone, *i.e.*, no cracks are formed, are termed “sub-threshold” and occur at small loads. Under these conditions, the relative track width and thus scratch resistance of a material relative to a reference is given by

$$\text{Scratch resistance (plasticity)} = (w_{\text{ref}}/w) \sim (H_{\text{ref}}/H)^{-1/2}. \quad (28)$$

The assumption in this prediction is that the contact details of load and shape are invariant such that the test material and the reference material are scratched in the same way. The hardness of the reference material is H_{ref} such that scratching produces a plastic deformation track of width w_{ref} . If the hardness of the test material is greater than that of the reference material, the track width is smaller and the scratch resistance of the test material by this measure, Eq. (28), is greater.

At greater “post-threshold” contact loads, lateral cracks are formed and the characteristic spatial parameter of the scratch is the lateral crack length c . Combining Eqs. (22) and (27) and imposing the equilibrium condition expressed in terms of toughness and modulus, replacing 2γ with the more conventionally used toughness T using $T^2 = 2\gamma E$ [Lawn, 1993], gives

$$\mathcal{G} \sim E(P/H)^{5/2}/c^4 \sim T^2/E, \quad (29)$$

where information regarding contact geometry has again been suppressed by approximating $M \sim E$. Inverting this expression gives the contact load and material dependence of lateral crack lengths at dragged contacts,

$$c \sim (P/H)^{5/8}E^{1/2}T^{-1/2}. \quad (30)$$

noting that Eq. (30) is somewhat similar in form to Eq. (27) but is extended by the the inclusion of elastic and fracture property dependencies. The form of Eq. (30) is typical for expressions developed in indentation fracture mechanics, in that material influences are represented by sequences of material properties raised to fractional powers [Lawn *et al.*, 1980; Marshall *et al.*, 1982], *e.g.*, Eq. (4). The relative crack length and thus scratch resistance of a material relative to a reference is given by

$$\text{Scratch resistance (fracture)} = (c_{\text{ref}}/c) \sim (H_{\text{ref}}/H)^{-5/8}(E_{\text{ref}}/E)^{1/2}(T_{\text{ref}}/T)^{-1/2}. \quad (31)$$

Once again, the assumption is that the contact load and shape are invariant. Scratching of the reference material produces a lateral crack of length c_{ref} . If the combination of properties given by Eq. (30) for the test material is greater than that for the reference material, the lateral crack is smaller and the scratch resistance of the test material by this measure, Eq. (31), is greater.

At even greater contact loads, the lateral cracks curve towards and intersect the material surface, removing chips of material such that the spatial parameter characterizing the scratch is the volume of material removed/length of scratch V_L . This parameter has the dimensions of area and varies as the cross-section of the plastic deformation zone-lateral crack complex, Figs. 3(b) and (c), such that

$$V_L \sim hc \sim w(h/w)c. \quad (32)$$

The last term in Eq. (32) has been written to reflect the fact that the parameter V_L , the line wear volume, is the product of three factors that exhibit different material dependencies of increasing complexity: plastic, elastic-plastic, elastic-plastic-fracture. Combining the requisite Eqs. (4), (27), and (30) into Eq. (32), suppressing geometrical and load dependencies and retaining only material dependencies gives

$$V_L \sim (1/H)^{1/2}(E/H)^{2/3}(1/H)^{5/8}E^{1/2}T^{-1/2} \quad (33)$$

The relative line wear volume and thus scratch resistance of a material relative to a reference is thus given by

$$\text{Scratch resistance (wear)} = (V_{Lref}/V_L) \sim (H_{ref}/H)^{-1.8}(E_{ref}/E)^{1.2}(T_{ref}/T)^{-0.5} \quad (34)$$

using decimal notation for simplicity. Once again, the assumption is that the contact load and shape are invariant. Scratching of the reference material produces a line wear volume of V_{Lref} . If the combination of properties given by Eq. (33) for the test material is greater than that for the reference material, the wear volume is smaller and the scratch resistance of the test material by this measure, Eq. (34), is greater.

Figure 6. Variation of predicted scratch resistance for the Mohs minerals assuming dominance by various phenomena and the lateral crack analysis developed here. The predicted volume of the wear track shows the greatest variation with Mohs number and is the most likely candidate for the basis of the Mohs scale.

Equations (28), (31), and (34) provide a means of assessing the relationship between material properties and Mohs number. Figure 6 shows a logarithmic plot of predicted scratch resistance as a function of Mohs number, assuming dominance by plastic, fracture, or wear effects using the above relationships and the material properties of the Mohs minerals. The ratios of the left sides of Eqs. (28), (31), and (34) were determined using apatite (Mohs number 5) as the reference and then normalizing the resulting values by those of talc (Mohs number 1) to generate a relative resistance for each parameter. The lower open symbols show the relative scratch resistance based on residual track width as determined by plasticity. The central open symbols show the relative scratch resistance based on lateral crack length as determined by fracture. The upper filled symbols show the relative scratch resistance based on volume of material removed as determined by wear.

It is instructive to consider Fig. 6 from the perspective of Mohs scale development. Relative scratch resistance determined by plastic effects (lower open symbols) varies by about a factor of 30 over the Mohs scale, and just over 10 if diamond is excluded. This in itself makes plastic track width a weak indicator of scratch resistance. In addition, to obtain experimentally viable track width measurements it is better to use small, sub-threshold contact loads such that the tracks are not deformed by cracking effects, *e.g.*, Fig. 1. Such tracks are small and difficult to observe and measure, even with an optical microscope in the laboratory. The data of Fig. 6 thus suggest that field identification and distinction of minerals by plastic track width comparison would be extremely difficult and thus it is unlikely that the Mohs scale was based on this phenomenon. Relative scratch resistance determined by fracture effects (central open symbols) varies by about a factor of 60 over the Mohs scale, and just over 20 if diamond is excluded. This makes crack length a better indicator of scratch resistance than track width, but not much. However, crack length measurements are also difficult, especially if the cracks are sub-surface in opaque or translucent materials. The data of Fig. 6 thus also suggest that field identification and distinction of minerals by comparison of lateral crack lengths at scratches would be difficult and thus it is unlikely that the Mohs scale was based on this phenomenon either.

In contrast to the above considerations, relative scratch resistance determined by wear effects (upper filled symbols) varies by about a factor of 10000 over the Mohs scale, and just over 1000

if diamond is excluded, making line wear volume a robust indicator of scratch resistance. Further, wear tracks, in which surface material is removed to form a linear flaw, are easy to observe and assess. The created sub-surface texture and orientation at the flaw is usually very different from that of the original surface allowing easy visual assessment in the field of the existence and scale of scratches, even in opaque or inhomogeneous materials. Hence, identification and distinction of minerals by line wear volume at scratches is relatively easy and thus it is likely that the Mohs scale was based on this phenomenon. The solid line in Fig. 6 is an empirical fit to the predicted scratch resistance of the form $\exp(N - 1)$, where N is the Mohs number and the use of $(N - 1)$ in the exponential emphasizes that the Mohs scale is relative, in this case based on mineral 1, talc. The exponential description also emphasizes that the material properties responses of different minerals are exaggerated by the scale. If the material properties dependence of scratch resistance by wear, Eqs. (33) and (34), is simplified and approximated as $H^2T^{1/2}/E$, the connection between Mohs number and conventional hardness, toughness, and modulus is

$$N \sim 2\ln H + (1/2)\ln T - \ln E - 1. \quad (35)$$

Equation (35) provides a physical basis for the empirical description of the Mohs scale detailed over 60 years ago by Tabor [Tabor, 1954, 1956] and often repeated graphically in textbooks [Callister, 1997], and emphasizes the dominance, but not exclusivity [Broz *et al.*, 2006], of hardness in determining Mohs number.

4. DISCUSSION and CONCLUSIONS

The analysis developed here to describe lateral cracks at linear sharp contacts considerably extends indentation fracture mechanics. Such mechanics has been well established for the median-radial crack system at point contacts [Lawn *et al.*, 1980; Anstis *et al.*, 1981; Cook, 2020], the lateral crack system at point contacts [Marshall *et al.*, 1982] and its interaction with median-radial cracks [Cook *et al.*, 1990], the strength of components controlled by median-radial cracks [Chantikul *et al.*, 1981], and the effect of lateral cracks at point contacts on such strengths [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015]. In addition, the fracture mechanics of median cracks

formed at linear wedge, roller, and dragged contacts and the resulting strengths is also well established [Swain and Lawn, 1976; Cook, 1994, 2017, 2018]. Here, the lengths of lateral cracks at linear flaws are described for flaws formed by static, rolled, or dragged sharp contacts at which the cracks are “well developed,” *i.e.*, much larger than the contact. This description is important for predicting engineering application and control of linear flaws, including optical quality of scratched surfaces, strengths resulting from scored lines, and edge quality of broken components. However, analysis of lateral cracks that are small with respect to contacts and in “initiation” states has not been considered here. Such analysis is important in the engineering contexts of defining maximum allowed energies, loads, or contact geometries required to avoid scratches. Initiation analyses should begin with the full $\mathcal{E}(c)$ expression of Eq. (20) and follow the fracture mechanics developed for median-radial cracks at indentation contacts in ceramics [Lawn and Evans, 1977; Lawn and Marshall, 1979].

A useful extension of the analysis would be to re-cast the earlier point contact lateral crack analysis [Marshall *et al.*, 1982] in energy terms as here, rather than as a force balance based on an equation similar to Eq. (4). Such re-casting would highlight the similarities and differences of the two geometries and provide insight in cases for which the distinction is unclear, for instance slow dragged or rolled contacts. An example of such convergence is the identical $c \sim P^{5/8}$ load dependence of well-developed lateral crack lengths predicted for point [Marshall *et al.*, 1982] and dragged, Eq. (23), contacts. Another extension of the analysis would be to consider crack lengths far from initiation adjacent to the deformation zone and at propagation termination by the surface. Geometric similarity of the contact would suggest that such exiting cracks should scale as $c \sim w$, an idea forwarded earlier in the context of wedge loading [Swain and Lawn, 1976] (for which, thus, $c \sim P$). This idea should be testable by determination of stress trajectories and bears directly on a major application of the analysis here—the prediction of wear volumes, scratch resistance, and interpretation of the Mohs scale in terms of material properties.

The underlying physical and analytical basis for the Mohs scale was provided by the analysis developed here, along with support for that basis through application of experimentally determined material properties and displayed in Fig. 6. The analysis would appear to answer many of the questions raised earlier [Broz *et al.*, 2006]: the physical process of cracking

associated with scratching is well defined, Fig. 3(c), leading to a clear definition of scratch resistance, Eq. (34), that is different from hardness and involves other material properties of toughness and modulus; a simple predictive relationship between material properties and Mohs number is provided, Eq. (35). The physical basis of experimental estimation of Mohs number—naked eye visual observation—would have been available to Mohs as a macroscopic test, implementable in the field. It is unclear that microscopic tests, based on specialized instrumentation in the laboratory [Gu and Yao, 2011; Bensaid *et al.*, 2018; Suratwala *et al.*, 2019; Zakiev *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2020], or nano-scale considerations including atomistic computation [Gerberich *et al.*, 2015] truly bear on the origin of the Mohs number as Mohs characterizes a macroscopic phenomenon. Both the microscopic tests and the nano-scale considerations bear on the onset of fracture at elastic-plastic scratching. Such tests and considerations are therefore important in assessing the mechanisms of crack initiation and applicability of the Mohs number to characterize a particular scratch. The fundamental basis of Mohs number appears to be not microscopic but macroscopic: hardness, toughness, and modulus combined to result in macroscopic scratch resistance defined as reciprocal line wear volume. Although there is no “Mohs hardness” or “scratch hardness,” hardness does play a primary role in determining Mohs number, as recognized by Tabor [Tabor, 1954, 1956]. Strictly, hardness is not material property, as it depends on the shape of the probe used to assess the mean contact pressure at a contact. Thus geometry and properties of the wearing asperity must play a secondary role in determining scratch resistance, a conclusion also recognized by Tabor.

A clear conclusion from this work is that *much* more experimental measurement of lateral cracking at linear sharp contacts is required. The survey work of Swain and the analysis here provide a robust framework for such measurements. The variation of flaw dimensions, track width and lateral crack length, with load for static contact by sharp wedges [Lawn and Swain, 1976], dragged contacts, Fig. 4 [Swain, 1979], and rolled contacts, Fig. 5 [Swain, 1985] should be extended to a variety of materials and contact geometries. The variation of wear volume and scratch resistance, Fig. 6, with material and the nature of the contacting asperity, in the contexts of the Mohs scale and engineering application, should be determined.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author gratefully acknowledges correspondence and many conversations regarding linear flaws and lateral cracking in over 40 years of collaboration with Drs. B.R. Lawn, D.B. Marshall, and M.V. Swain. Dr Swain is thanked for the provision of the raw data for Fig. 5.

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